

Investigating the Influence of Farmers' Connectedness to Nature and Place Attachment on Soil Conservation Practices in Thailand

***Wanippol Mahaarcha**

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1578-4182>

Somsak Amornsiriphong

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8892-6283>

Yuthpong Chantrawarin

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-3293-9153>

Department of Social Sciences, Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Mahidol University, Nakhon Pathom, 73170, Thailand

*Corresponding Author Email: wanippol@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Soil erosion, which causes land degradation, is negatively impacting the world's agriculture and food security. Conservation of soil fertility is thus crucial for sustainable land and agricultural production. Several previous research works, regardless of whether they are conducted in developing or developed countries, indicate that connectedness to nature and place attachment among farmers are studied to test whether and how these variables affect farmers' soil conservation intentions and behaviours.

Objective: This study aims to investigate the interplay between farmers' environmental connectedness, their attachment to place, and their soil conservation practices.

Methodology: This quantitative, cross-sectional study employed a descriptive survey design. Data were collected from 351 farmers in Saiyok District, Kanchanaburi Province, Thailand, via a structured questionnaire. The research model utilised scores for nature connectedness and four dimensions of place attachment (place identity, place dependence, nature bonding, and family bonding) to examine their influence on soil conservation efforts.

Results: Regression analysis revealed that two dimensions of place attachment—place identity and place dependence—have a statistically significant positive effect on farmers' soil conservation efforts. Conversely, nature bonding was found to have a statistically significant negative effect on conservation. Furthermore, the overall variable of connectedness to nature showed no significant relationship with soil conservation efforts.

Conclusion: The more positive place identity and place dependence that Thai farmers feel, the more likely they are to practice soil conservation. In addition, the influence of nature connectedness on soil conservation is not found in this context.

Unique Contribution: This study has contributed to the understanding of the influence of place attachment that affect Thai farmers' soil conservation practices. This study also highlighted the importance of natural and environmental worldviews among Thai farmers that are different from Westerner environmental worldviews.

Key Recommendation: Our results provide instructive recommendations for the government to promote soil conservation practices among farmers in terms of promoting activities that foster a sense of belonging and stewardship, communicating with farmers by focusing on the land's functional value and the importance of agricultural production, and providing financial incentives or subsidies for conservation to lower-income farmers.

Keywords: Connectedness to nature; place attachment; soil conservation

Introduction

Soil erosion, which causes land degradation, is negatively impacting the world's agriculture and food security. Governments around the world are focusing on finding solutions to soil erosion. Evidence shows that the rate of soil fertility decline is severe, with 75 billion metric tons of soil eroded annually from farmland worldwide (FAO, 2017). Increased production through improved technology, more intensive land management, and increased fertiliser use may lead to continued soil degradation, requiring a higher capacity to provide ecosystem services. Human activities can cause soil degradation through their behaviours in response to environmental changes. As a result, systematic investigations of the behaviours and the factors affecting them are important in the area of soil conservation.

Farmers' soil conservation relating to ecosystem maintenance has become a topic of fundamental importance. Previous research on farmers' conservation and pro-environmental behaviours has generally focused on economic drivers (Zhang et al., 2019). However, economic factor is not the only factor that influences farmers' pro-environmental behaviours. No single factor dominates farmers' decisions over their needs; nonetheless, a systematic review suggests the integration of social and psychological factors (Prokopy et al., 2019). Recently, however, a study has identified psychological factors that are significant in farmers' decisions on soil conservation and pro-environmental practices (Li et al., 2024). These include mention of various elements broadly attributable to connectedness or connection to nature and place attachment. Notwithstanding, there is little research available to understand how connectedness to nature and place attachment may influence soil conservation on farms.

Previous research shows that conservation and pro-environmental behaviour increase with human connection to nature (Gosling & Williams, 2010). The self-perception of one's connection to the natural world reflects an individual's sense of kinship and emotional experience of connection to nature (Mayer et al., 2009). An individual's willingness and subsequent behaviours to protect the environment are influenced to a certain degree by their connection to nature. Connectedness to nature can drive farmers' commitment to soil conservation and promote beneficial behaviours among farmers (Richardson et al., 2020).

There is also a remarkable interest in understanding how place attachment and environmentally friendly behaviours are related. An emotional bond connects positively between an individual and a place of attachment. Place attachment covers individuals, psychological processes, and place dimensions. The relationship between place attachment and environmentally friendly behaviours has recently garnered research attention. The study highlighted the importance of place attachment in activating farmers' conservation intentions and behaviours (Gosling & Williams, 2010).

The concept of connectedness to nature and place attachment is viewed differently in the Western and Thai contexts. The Western perspective has a tradition of dualism that often views nature as something distinct from human culture, whereas Thai Buddhist culture perceives an inseparable bond between humans and nature (Teerapong et al., 2025). In addition, Western farmers' place attachment is frequently more individualised and linked with financial gain and personal legacy. In contrast, Thai farmers' place attachment may involve more extensive familial and community connections (Masngammuang & Chumchong, 2019). Nevertheless, it appears that most studies on the relationship between oneness with nature, connection with nature, place attachment, and conservation behaviour have been predominantly tested in the developed world. In contrast, the context of Thailand has not been the case so far. This study aims to understand the soil conservation practices of Thai farmers in highland areas, which are vulnerable to soil erosion due to steep terrain and high rainfall. The problem of land misuse has become a serious problem in Thailand, particularly on steep land with no conservation exercise (Wijitkosum, 2016). Therefore, the behaviour of farmers' connectedness to nature and place attachment in increasing soil conservation practices is crucial to examine in Thailand. To preserve soil fertility and promote sustainable agricultural production in the future, it is vital to thoroughly examine and replace unsuitable soil management practices with soil conservation practices.

The objective of this research is to address the relationship between connectedness to nature, place attachment, and soil conservation among farmers in Saiyok District, Kanchanaburi Province, Thailand. We hypothesised that connectedness to nature and place attachment have a positive relationship with soil conservation among Thai farmers. We hope that the results of this research will contribute to a better approach to agricultural and environmental policies in Thailand and worldwide, particularly in promoting environmental conservation activities and participation in rural agricultural areas that emphasise unity with nature.

Literature Review

Connectedness to nature

Connectedness to nature is an individual's feeling of being a part of and a sense of affiliation with nature. It is an individual's emotional and cognitive feelings regarding connection with nature and belonging to nature. It can be enhanced through outdoor activities and nature-related tasks, benefiting mental well-being and helping to formulate pro-environmental attitudes, as well as contributing to more sustainable behaviours and relationships with the natural world (Richardson et al., 2020).

Many scholars have developed numerous measures of connectedness to nature, both explicit and implicit (Schultz et al., 2004; Mayer et al., 2009). Explicit measures employ controlled processes

that are slow, deliberate, and exert effortful control, requiring full cognitive capacity and higher-order psychological processing. Implicit measures examine automatic processes. An associative network may cause the process to go fast, unintentionally, involuntarily, or effortlessly.

Place attachment

Place attachment refers to the general emotions, ties, ideas, and behavioural intentions that people develop in their connection to their social and physical surroundings over time. It describes the individual and emotional bond that people or groups form with a specific place, shaped by their experiences, remembrances, and impressions of that place. Place attachment has been considered a construct comprising multiple dimensions, including place dependence, place identity, place affect, and place social bond. Previous scholars have developed several measures of place attachment (Jorgensen & Stedman, 2001; Raymond et al., 2010). Jorgensen and Stedman (2001) formulated a conceptualisation of place attachment. It helps measure place attachment along three sub-dimensions: conative, cognitive, and affect. Later, Raymond and colleagues (2010) developed a 20-item place attachment scale, which underlines dimensions of place identity, place dependence, nature bonding, and social bonding.

Soil conservation

In terms of management strategies, the purpose of soil conservation is to practice farming operations that control soil erosion. Soil conservation strategies help prevent or reduce soil particle detachment and the flow of water and/or air through the soil. These strategies inhibit soil contamination and prevent the loss of the topmost layer of soil and fertility (Ogunsola et al., 2021). To ensure the long-term use of soil for future generations, various types of soil conservation methods should be employed to maintain its productivity. Under these management strategies, conservation approaches such as conservation tillage, contour farming, strip cropping, and planting windbreaks are also recommended to be held on.

Farmer's behaviours: Connectedness to nature, place attachment, and soil conservation

Mayer and colleagues (2009) found that a key determinant of environmental behaviour and subjective well-being is a connection to nature. Previous evidence has also confirmed that a connection to nature can lead to various pro-environmental behaviours and promote sustainable practices (Gosling & Williams, 2010). The place of living and working significantly influences the time spent in nature. Contacting nature, along with caring about it, is necessary to inspire people to act ecologically (Lumber et al., 2017). Also, there is evidence proving a connection between nature and pro-environmental behaviour connectedness. Ones with a greater feeling of connectedness to nature act pro-environmentally than ones with a lower feeling of connectedness to nature (Mayer et al., 2009). For the farmer's conservation behaviour, Gosling and Williams (2010) found that connection with nature helps increase vegetation protection behaviours. Of course, tree-planting and remnant vegetation management depend on farmers' attitudes about connectedness to nature.

Conceptually, place attachment can influence behaviour that likely stimulates positive environmental concerns for individuals living. Various studies have confirmed a positive

association between place attachment and pro-environmental behaviours (Gosling & Williams, 2010; Li et al., 2023). Halpenny (2010) found that place attachment was associated with the intention of pro-environmental behaviour of park visitors. The positive impact of place attachment on deciding to maintain land was higher when the place attachment was high, as in the agricultural land conversion, as found by Prayitno and colleagues (2021). From the literature reviews above, the present study can draw the hypothesis that farmers who hold a higher level of connectedness to nature and place attachment will exhibit a higher level of soil conservation behaviours.

Methodology

Population and sample

This study is a quantitative research, using a structured questionnaire as a tool for collecting data. The population of this study consisted of farmers aged 20 years and above who worked in the agricultural sector as their primary occupation and resided in Saiyok District, Kanchanaburi Province, Thailand. Based on the Krejcie and Morgan formula for sample size calculation, there were 351 households selected as the sample for this study from the total population of 3,531 registered farm operating households. The sample was obtained from a list of households operating farms registered by the Department of Agricultural Extension, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives. The present study employed a three-stage sampling to select the sample. The first stage involved selecting two sub-districts from a total of seven sub-districts using simple random sampling. The second stage involved selecting two villages from each sub-district using simple random sampling. The third stage involved selecting registered farm operating households in each of the selected villages through systematic random sampling, where the sample was randomly selected at predetermined intervals. One person from the household has been selected to be the respondent and fill in the questionnaire, and we regard them as a representative of the household.

Measures

The questionnaire consisted of five parts, covering socio-economic characteristics, connectedness to nature, place attachment, soil conservation, and suggestions. (To be noted here, each item in the questionnaire has been rephrased (as shown in Tables 1-3) to capture the abstract relationship between farmers' connectedness to nature, place attachment, and soil conservation.)

Connectedness to nature: The present study employed the Connectedness to Nature Scale (CNS), created by Mayer and colleagues (2009), to assess the level of connectedness to nature among farmers ($\alpha = .84$, $n = 60$). The original CNS contains 14 items on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly agree" to "disagree strongly," to rate the respondent's feeling of connectedness to nature. However, while trying out the questionnaire, the researchers used a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire and found the problem of midpoint-inflated responses. This might be due to the cultural characteristics of Thai people. Thai culture emphasises the need to fit in with others and avoid conflict in society. Compared to Western survey replies, Asian survey responses are typically more prone to central tendency bias (Westland, 2022). The present study generates only 4-point scale items (0 = strongly disagree, 1 = somewhat disagree, 2 = somewhat agree, and 3 = strongly agree) and deletes the "neutral" scale (neither agree nor disagree) for the reason that it attempts to avoid neutral responses. After trying out the questionnaire, 7 items of CNS are reliable

for analysis in this study. As a result of the study, the score of the internal reliability of the connectedness to nature is adequate ($\alpha = .67$).

Table 1: Connectedness to nature.

Connectedness to nature	Mean	S.D.	Alpha
Belonging to the natural world community	2.74	0.45	.67
Sense of oneness with the natural world	2.71	0.47	
Understanding of how actions affect natural worlds	2.66	0.50	
Recognition and appreciation of other organisms' intelligence	2.61	0.50	
Equal-mutual belonging to the earth	2.56	0.58	
Kinship with animals and plants	2.41	0.56	
Feeling embedded in the broader natural world	2.30	0.61	
Total	17.99	2.13	

Place attachment: This study adopted the place attachment scale, developed by Raymond and colleagues (2010), comprising five place attachment dimensions (place dependence, place identity, nature bonding, family bonding, and friend bonding). The mentioned original place attachment items comprised 20 scale items, ranging from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. Nevertheless, this study generates only 4-point scale items, the same as the connectedness to nature score. To explore the structure of place attachment, Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was employed. An orthogonal rotation (using the varimax method) was employed. Suggested by Raymond and colleagues, the scale to interpret the PCA consists of five dimensions. All items loaded highly in each component except for “Moving out from the place if without family.” This item was excluded from the place attachment component of family bonding.

After conducting internal reliability testing, we found that the friend bonding component did not demonstrate acceptable reliability (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.54), so we excluded it from subsequent analyses. In contrast, the components assessing place dependence, place identity, nature bonding, and family bonding all exhibited satisfactory internal reliability, as indicated by their respective Cronbach’s alpha coefficients (see Table 2).

Table 2: Place attachment components and factor loading coefficient.

Category	Items	Factor loading	Mean	S.D.	Alpha
Place identity					0.82
	Sense of belonging to the place	0.77	2.65	0.50	
	Strong identification with the place	0.74	2.70	0.47	
	Deep meaning of this place	0.73	2.71	0.47	
	A tie of personal identity to the place	0.69	2.61	0.50	
	Attachment to the place	0.64	2.74	0.47	
	Special significance to the place	0.62	2.65	0.49	

Place dependence				0.73
	Irreplaceability of the place for activities	0.85	2.56	0.66
	Preference for the place for activities	0.74	2.50	0.63
	Incomparable nature of the place	0.66	2.63	0.53
	Ideal location for preferred activities	0.60	1.96	0.79
Nature bonding				0.68
	Deep oneness with the natural environment	0.72	2.34	0.64
	Inner peace in the natural environment	0.67	1.80	0.76
	Strong attachment to the natural environment	0.67	2.09	0.72
	Decreased attachment without native plants and animals	0.62	2.36	0.62
	Self-discovery through time in the natural environment	0.58	1.98	0.73
Family bonding				0.65
	Living in the place because of the family	0.86	2.81	0.48
	Special relationships with family in the place	0.73	2.66	0.57

Soil conservation was the dependent variable in the present study, which included contour farming, conservation tillage, planting windbreaks, cover cropping, and crop rotation (Table 3). This dependent variable is continuous and comes from the combination of all five four-point scale items (0 = never, 1 = rarely, 2 = often, 3 = always).

Table 3: Soil conservation.

Soil conservation	Mean	Std. Deviation
Contour farming	2.52	1.05
Conservation tillage	2.50	1.01
Planting windbreaks	1.43	1.47
Cover cropping	0.61	1.14
Crop rotation	0.50	1.03
Total	7.56	3.28

Other variables: Other variables in this study cover sex, age, years of schooling, size of household, household income per month, original hometown, duration of residing in the present area, duration of working in the agricultural sector, land size, type of plantation, and belonging to a community group or organisation.

Analysis

Since the dependent variable, soil conservation, is continuous, multiple regression analysis was employed to investigate the impact of connectedness to nature and place attachment on soil conservation among farmers in Thailand.

Results

A total of 351 respondents were received, and they were almost equally divided by gender (male = 51.6%, female = 48.4%). The mean age was 51.4. The average years of schooling were 11 years. The mean household size was 3.5 members per household. On average, the household income was approximately 24,960 baht (approximately \$ 715) per month. Approximately 64.1% of the residents consider Saiyok District their original hometown. The average duration of residing in Saiyok District was 33 years, while the average duration of working in the agricultural sector was 15 years. The average land size for agriculture was 12 rai (about 4.7 acres). More than half of the respondents (61%) have field crops as their primary plantations, including cassava, corn, and sugarcane. Few respondents (5.7%) belonged to a community group or organisation.

Table 4 presents two regression models, with soil conservation as the dependent variable. At the bottom of each model, displaying the R^2 value and explaining by all the predictors, shows the total amount of variance in soil conservation.

Initially, we focused on the relationship between soil conservation and socio-economic factors in Model 1. Households' monthly household income had a positive and significant influence on soil conservation. Farmers from Saiyok District and other districts in Kanchanaburi Province reported higher adoption of soil conservation practices than those from other provinces. It was found that farmers who had a longer duration of working in the agricultural sector practised less soil conservation. Farmers who planted a field crop had significantly less practice in soil conservation than those who planted other crops.

In Model 2, we added connectedness to nature score and all place attachment dimensions. Compared to the previous model, the effects of socio-economic factors did not change tremendously. The results showed that connectedness to nature did not influence soil conservation. For the place attachment dimensions, place identity and place dependence were positively associated with soil conservation. Nevertheless, nature bonding was negatively associated with soil conservation.

Note that Model 2, which takes into account connectedness to nature and place attachment dimensions, explains the soil conservation practice much better than Model 1. The R^2 increased significantly from model 1 (26%) to model 2 (32%).

Table 4: Regression output providing the relationship of farmers' connectedness to nature, place attachment, and soil conservation.

Variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	Beta	S.E.	Beta	S.E.

(Constant)	6.87***	(1.69)	2.88***	(2.13)
Female	0.02	(.32)	-0.07	(.31)
Age	0.01	(.02)	-0.01	(.02)
Years of schooling	-0.04	(.05)	-0.05	(.05)
Household size	-0.21	(.13)	-0.14	(.13)
Monthly income (× 10,000 baht)	0.61***	(.00)	0.53***	(.00)
Original hometown				
Other provinces (Ref.)				
Saiyok District	1.48**	(.50)	1.36**	(.49)
Other districts in Kanchanaburi Province	1.71**	(.55)	1.32*	(.55)
Duration of residing in the present area	0.02	(.01)	0.01	(.01)
Duration of working in the agricultural sector	-0.05*	(.02)	-0.03	(.02)
Land size	0.02	(.02)	0.02	(.02)
Planting a field crop	-2.59***	(.34)	-2.58***	(.33)
Belonging to a community group	0.13	(.71)	0.32	(.70)
Connectedness to nature			-0.02	(.05)
Place identity			0.18*	(.09)
Place dependence			0.26**	(.09)
Nature bonding			-0.18*	(.07)
Family bonding			0.30	(.18)
R ²	0.26		0.31	

Note: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$.

Discussion

This study intended to examine the relationship between connectedness to nature, place attachment, and soil conservation among farmers in Saiyok District, Kanchanaburi Province, Thailand. For regression analysis, connectedness to nature was used as a single variable, while place attachment was classified into four subdimensional dimensions (place identity, place dependence, nature bonding, and family bonding). They were used separately to examine the relationship with soil conservation.

It revealed that, under the place attachment dimension, place identity and place dependence had a positive influence on soil conservation practices. The high farmers' place identity indicated the consistency between their place image and their self-image. Farmers with a strong sense of identity with place are more aware of environmental issues and feel a moral obligation to protect the soil in their farming place. They are also more motivated to preserve the quality and features of their farmland that are central to their self-concept and values (Li et al., 2023). Place identity is a significant intrinsic motivation for landowners and residents to actively participate in soil conservation efforts, particularly in protecting the places of attachment and identification.

For place dependence, this study showed that place dependence can influence soil conservation practices among farmers. Consistent with previous studies in Asian contexts (Li et al., 2023; Valizadeh et al., 2020), the empirical results indicate a positive relationship between place dependence and conservation behaviour, which contributes to a deeper emotional bond with the land. The possible explanation may be that farmers with a deeper emotional bond to the land tend to prioritise its long-term well-being and sustainability over short-term benefit.

Surprisingly, it was found that nature bonding had a negative influence on soil conservation practices, while connectedness to nature did not have a statistically significant effect on soil conservation practices. By definition, nature bonding refers to the development of a strong emotional connection between humans and natural places (Raymond et al., 2010), and connectedness to nature refers to an individual feeling as a part of nature (Schultz et al., 2004). Since oneness with nature is the key to both nature bonding and connectedness to nature, it is essential to discuss the concepts and views of nature and the environment among Thai farmers. Anthropocentric values, where nature is perceived as a provider of sustenance, social well-being, and a healthy livelihood, have shaped how rural Thai people understand nature and the environment. Whereas eco-centric views are considerably emerging among the younger Thai people, i.e., humans are part of nature (Panya & Sirisai, 2003). In general, Thai farmers view nature as “a world around us”. Such a view of nature provides them with the resources of food necessary for survival. Individuals with an anthropocentric view supported the idea that human standards of living are a priority and argued that it is necessary to protect nature for the sake of human life. Furthermore, Thailand’s National Economic and Social Development Plans served as the core national plan, acting as a framework for economic and social development and influencing various organs of Thailand. They were initially launched in 1961 and adjusted every five years. In the early plans, they mainly focused on economic development, which did not include environmental issues in the plan. Environmental and sustainable development were initially included in the national plan in the early 1990s. As a result, concepts of nature and environment among lay Thai people are still developing to be eco-centric. From this perspective, it can be argued that anthropocentric understandings of the natural environment of Thai farmers have rendered the cognitive process of intention to protect the non-human natural environment and natural landscapes less effective. This can explain the negative relationship between nature bonding and soil conservation, as well as the absence of an association between connectedness to nature and soil conservation. The result contradicts a previous study that identified a connection to nature as a reliable predictor of pro-environmental behaviour (Burnham et al., 2023).

Additionally, the results of the current study suggest that connectedness to nature has not had a statistically significant impact on soil conservation practices. It is also possible that connectedness to nature may indirectly influence soil conservation through the values and attitudes of individuals and communities towards the environment. Pereira and Forster (2015) found that environmental values partly mediate the relationship between connectedness to nature and pro-environmental behaviours, suggesting that stronger environmental values and greater engagement in pro-environmental actions can enhance one's sense of connectedness to nature. Gosling and Williams (2010) proposed that environmental concern, closely aligned with the subscale of Schultz's (2004) scale, fully mediates the connection between connectedness to nature and pro-environmental

actions. Since the findings of this study do not establish statistical causality in this relationship, further research is needed to explore a causal link between connectedness to nature and soil conservation within the Thai context.

This study provides evidence that farmers who originated from Saiyok District and other districts in Kanchanaburi Province reported higher soil conservation practices than those from other provinces. This result implied that the place of origin is often closely tied to an individual's sense of identity, which can contribute to a strong emotional bond. The intense remembrance of childhood places may evoke deep memories, emotional bonds, and a range of emotions (i.e., happiness, sorrow, identity, a sense of security) through the spatial setting. The attachment to one's place of origin can strengthen a sense of stewardship and care for the environment. A strong emotional bond with the land can create participation in soil conservation practices that maintain soil fertility and mitigate soil degradation (Prayitno et al., 2021).

Additionally, higher-income farmers tend to adopt soil conservation practices due to their greater ability to adapt to them. Wealthier farmers not only have a higher likelihood of having more resources to invest in conservation, but they are also able to access extension support. In contrast, lower-income farmers tend to adopt less, as they may be constrained in their potential to invest in soil conservation. Lower-income farmers may prioritise short-term production over long-term sustainability, as poverty can hinder their ability to adopt sustainable practices.

Conclusion

Throughout the comprehensive investigation, this article presents results on connectedness to nature and place attachment that influence farmers' soil conservation practices, based on survey data collected from 351 farm-operating households in Kanchanaburi Province, Thailand. The key findings are as follows: (1) A farmer's sense of place identity and place dependence have statistically positively affected soil conservation. This confirms that a deep-rooted sense of place identity and place dependence does play a role in motivating long-term protection of their land and environmental behaviour. (2) Farmers' sense of nature bonding has statistically negatively affected soil conservation. This result highlights the importance of natural and environmental worldviews among Thai farmers, which differ from Western environmental worldviews. (3) Connectedness to nature has no significant relationship with soil conservation. It may be because connectedness to nature has an indirect influence on soil conservation practices.

Drawing from the above conclusions, we suggest these following policies: (1) The government should emphasize encouraging the attractiveness and meaning of rural places to raise a conservationist identity and pro-environmental behaviours among farmers, such as promoting activities that foster a sense of belonging and stewardship, e.g., community farming events, and highlighting the unique cultural, historical, or natural features of the local landscape. (2) When communicating with farmers about promoting soil conservation practices, the government should focus on the land's functional value and the importance of agricultural production. This strengthens the sense of locality and the significance of soil conservation. By designing conservation programs and policies that are consistent with farmers' place dependence and the

characteristics of their local environment, tailoring suitable practices to the specific context enhances their relevance and adoption. (3) The government should provide financial incentives or subsidies for conservation (e.g., tax deductions) to lower-income farmers, which target promoting conservation adoption. As farmers become more affluent, they may be more able to invest in soil conservation.

This study highlights the influence of place attachment that affects Thai farmers' soil conservation practices. Using the framework of place attachment, raising farmers' deeper emotional bonds to their land can enhance soil conservation in developing countries. When farmers view their land as more than just an asset, they are more likely to take care of it. For any agricultural initiative to succeed in promoting long-term care for the farmland, it is crucial to recognise farmers' emotional attachment to their land. Effective initiatives must address the feelings and meanings people hold about their land. In the developing world, people often develop a strong attachment to their local area due to persistent poverty and a heavy reliance on their community and natural resources. Place attachment is not just an emotional concept; it strongly motivates farmers to engage in conservation and other eco-friendly activities. When farmers feel a strong connection to their surroundings, that feeling motivates them to take actions that protect the environment in which they live. There is still a need for further research to see how connectedness to nature and place attachment affect conservation practices over the long term, particularly in developing countries. The long-term impact of those factors is far from fully understood.

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